

DECOMPOSITION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN HOMOGENEOUS MIXTURES

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The homogeneous decomposition of decinormal hydrogen peroxide in presence of a number of salts has been studied mostly at 35°. It is found that no cation is a catalyst unless it can exist in two states of oxidation. A simple mechanism of decomposition involving activated hydrogen peroxide molecules (but no free radicals) has been suggested which explains the first order decomposition with respect to the peroxide and the lowering of the corresponding velocity constant at low concentrations.

From the survey of the work done on the characteristics of decomposition of H_2O_2 in solution in presence of homogeneous as well as heterogeneous catalysts, the decomposition appears to be suppressed to a larger or smaller degree by hydrogen ions, in both cases. The soluble catalysts, limited in number, are almost invariably cations, capable of existence in more than one oxidised state, e.g., iron, copper and manganese ions. Bromine is also a good catalyst and is an example of an anion. On the other hand, heterogeneous catalysts are numerous (Thenard, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1818, ii, 9, 441, et seq, quoted by Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. 1, p. 936, 1935, London).

Oxygen gas is evolved, and therefore water must be the other product of decomposition. In the absence of a catalyst, although the rate is greatly reduced, the reaction is still possible; it is depressed by H^+ and accelerated by OH^- . It appears that the simplest mechanism, which corresponds to these reactions, can be expressed as:

When two molecules of H_2O_2 react, one molecule of oxygen and two molecules of water are produced. The ionisation (a) may, of course, take place in two steps, and it being a simple ionisation is expected to be much faster than (b), so that increase of $[H^+]$ will depress $[O_2^{2-}]$, thereby depressing the rate at which oxygen is evolved. The ionisation (a) must be quite small since the conductivity of aqueous hydrogen peroxide is reported to be small, although the results are not conclusive since it is difficult to find a suitable electrode (Newton Friend, "Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. VII, Part I, p. 332, 1924, London).

Presence of catalysts like Fe^{2+} greatly increases the rate of decomposition even when stabilisers are present. Perhaps the simplest mechanism to account for the same can be expressed as follows:

(b') is again a reaction between ions and likely to be fast, but (c') is not such a reaction. It appears that (c') should determine the overall rate in this case. In the uncatalysed reaction, the discharge of O_2^{2-} and the production of OH^- ions (which remove hydrogen ions produced in a) take place in the same step, the reaction involving H_2O_2 . In the catalysed reaction, they take place in two different steps, the reactions involving Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions.

On the other hand, Haber and Weiss (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **A147**, 332) consider a more complicated mechanism necessary for the reaction. The mechanism involves production of free radicals, OH and HO_2 . Thus, for the decomposition catalysed by ferrous ions they conclude that

When excess H_2O_2 is present, the reaction goes beyond oxidation of Fe^{2+} , and O_2 is produced. When one starts with Fe^{3+} ions as catalysts, some of them are first reduced,

after which oxygen is evolved according to the previous mechanism. Barb *et al.* (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, **47**, 475, 593) agree that the free radicals-OH, HO_2^- are formed, but consider that oxygen is evolved not by reaction (iv) or (vi) but as

If this mechanism is substantially correct, it should be unlikely to come across an ion catalyst which does not have two oxidation states. A search of the literature did not produce a very clear picture. We presume that the vagueness is due to self-decomposition of H_2O_2 , even when mildly stabilised, and different experimenters having used different conditions. Consequently, we decided to examine a number of salts at the same concentration of peroxide, keeping other conditions also as similar as possible.

EXPERIMENTAL

Catalytic Decomposition by Ferric Sulphate

Although a good deal of work was done on the role of ferric salts as catalysts, in view of the very rapid hydrolysis of these salts at low concentrations (Mellor, *loc. cit.*, Vol. 14, pp. 46, 51 et seq; Gyani and Misra, this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 499), we were curious to know what would happen if the salt concentrations were greatly reduced.

Stock solutions of normal ferric sulphate and $0.4N-H_2O_2$ were prepared. Peroxide (25 c.c.) was taken in a volumetric flask, ferric sulphate (50 c.c.) added to it and the mixture was then diluted to 100 c.c. Ten c.c. portions of the mixture were withdrawn after 10, 20 120 minutes and titrated with $N/10-KMnO_4$. Similar other experiments were performed in which the volume of ferric sulphate was decreased to 5, 2.5, 1.25, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.125 c.c. The rate of decomposition at 35° was found rapid so long as the mixture was at least $0.125 N$ with respect to ferric sulphate, over 80% decomposing in the first 20 minutes. Less than 2% was left after 100 mins.

FIG. 1
 Catalysis by Ferric sulph. solns.

As the concentration of the salt was further decreased, there was a rapid fall in the rate (vide Fig. 1). The catalytic activity enormously decreases as one goes from $0.005 N$ to $0.0025 N$. The decomposition in $0.0006 N$ salt is detectable after 2 hours. A visible

hydrolysis of the salt takes place at 0.005 *N*. The oxide formed is finer as the concentration of the salt is decreased, and the time required for settling of the precipitate is increased from 20 to 80 minutes as the concentration is decreased to 0.0012 *N*. The loss of activity consequent upon the decrease of free ferric ions is remarkable. We realised in this work that the p_H in the various mixtures could not be the same. To see the effect of p_H , we selected the mixture in which the iron salt was 0.025 *N*. Suitable buffer mixtures were added in such volumes that after final dilution with distilled water, the solution had p_H 1, 2, 3 6. The first three involved KCl-HCl mixtures, while the last three were adjusted with sodium acetate-acetic acid mixtures. The results are shown in Fig. 2A. It appears curious at first sight that the rate increases at first with increasing p_H , but a reversal sets in at p_H 3. However, in sodium acetate-acetic acid mixtures, there is the possibility of removal of ferric ions by complex formation, which again supports the view that the free Fe^{3+} is the catalyst. One should expect that progressive addition of sodium fluoride should likewise produce a corresponding depression in the catalytic activity. This is actually seen in Fig. 2A. Subsequently, we adjusted the p_H of the mixture by known amounts of HCl or H_2SO_4 . Instead of calculating the p_H , we measured it on a Beckman p_H -meter and found a uniform increase in the decomposition rate with the increase in p_H . The p_H of the practically neutral ferric sulphate was 2.35 to 2.40; so it was not possible to adjust the value at a higher figure by decreasing the amount of acid. The same appears to be true of 0.5*N*- $CuSO_4$. Although the presence of a small amount of acid does not affect appreciably the p_H of the neutral ferric sulphate, it unexpectedly produces an improvement on the value of *k*, perhaps by suppressing the rate of hydrolysis, unless the increase represents a salt effect (Fig. 2B).

TABLE I

Acid.	Ferric sulphate.		Acid.	Copper sulphate.	
	p_H .	<i>k</i> .		p_H .	<i>k</i> .
Nil	2.35	0.0284	HCl	1.45	0.00072
HCl	1.00	0.0061	HCl	2.40	0.00342
HCl	1.95	0.0189	H_2SO_4	1.50	0.00122
HCl	2.35	0.0316	H_2SO_4	2.35	0.00302
H_2SO_4	2.35	0.0156			
H_2SO_4	2.00	0.0031			

Catalysis by Cupric Sulphate and Ceric Ammonium Nitrate

Experiments with copper sulphate and ceric ammonium nitrate showed that the activity was much less even when enough of these salts was present (Fig. 3). In absence of acid, less than 10% of the peroxide was decomposed in the first 10 minutes, and barely 20% in 120 minutes. 0.15*N*- $CuSO_4$ at 25° hardly showed any activity. The decomposition in presence of neutral ceric nitrate was somewhat better initially. When acid was added to these mixtures, there was a definite fall in the rate of decomposition (Fig. 2B). It is curious that HCl and H_2SO_4 do not produce identical results.

It will be seen that there is no sudden increase in the rate of decomposition as the concentration of Cu^{2+} is increased. This is natural since copper ions do not undergo extensive hydrolysis like iron ions. On the other hand, catalysis by Ce^{4+} is again curious. There is a large rate at the beginning which, we believe, is due to Ce^{4+} ions.

FIG. 3
Catalysis by CuSO_4 solus.

But hydrolysis soon sets in so that the subsequent rate is quite slow, which, we presume, is due to cerous oxide. Almost all the ceric ions were reduced to cerous since ceric nitrate in the concentration used did not produce any precipitate till peroxide was added. It is also well known that H_2O_2 may be quantitatively estimated with ceric salts (Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 311, 1935, Longmans, Green & Co., London).

Catalysis by Potassium Iodide and Manganous Sulphate

The action of iodide ions in presence of increasing quantities of sulphuric acid was also studied. We prepared mixtures of 0.08*N*-H₂O₂ and 0.4*N*-KI. The total volume of oxygen evolved in 10 minutes was measured and converted to grams, the mixtures being maintained at 35°, with the following results.

TABLE II

Acid in mixture	Nil	<i>N</i> /1600	<i>N</i> /800	<i>N</i> /400	<i>N</i> /200	<i>N</i> /100
Oxygen (g.)	0.03064	0.03055	0.03051	0.03045	0.02948	0.02876

The total oxygen expected was 0.0320 g., so that when only small quantities of acid were present, the evolution was complete within a few per cent. But in *N*/100-acid, about 10% of the oxygen failed to appear. It appears therefore that the possibility of oxidation of iodide ions to iodine exists in such solutions:

However, in earlier works iodide ion was considered to be oxidised in alkaline solutions by peroxide, the reaction being purely catalytic in neutral solutions (Bredig and Walton, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1903, 9, 114, quoted by Newton Friend, *loc. cit.*, p. 338). V₂O₂Cl₄ was found to be another good catalyst. A solution, which was 0.125 *N*-H₂O₂ and 0.0225 *M*-V₂O₂Cl₄, showed 67% loss of peroxide in 10 minutes.

Mixtures were also prepared containing 0.10*N*-H₂O₂ and increasing concentrations of manganous sulphate. The catalytic power increased with increasing concentration of the salt. The first order rate constants at 35° were found to be 0.00058 at 0.25 *M*, 0.0015 at 1.3 *M*, 0.0039 at 2.5 *M* and 0.0127 at 4 *M* salt. The graph of the velocity constant, *k*, against salt concentration is shaped like a rectangular hyperbola, showing that increase in the concentration of MnSO₄ beyond 4 *N* would not produce a further increase in *k*.

DISCUSSION

If *a* is the initial concentration of H₂O₂ and *x*, the amount decomposed at time *t* minutes, $\log a/(a-x) = kt$, if the reaction is of the first order. Figs. 1-3 show the plots of $\log a/(a-x)$ against time. The graphs are approximately straight lines in limited number of cases and deviate towards decreased values of *k*, when the concentration of H₂O₂ becomes small in any experiment due to the reaction.

No new substance accumulates in the system as the decomposition progresses. Whereas the concentration of a catalyst remains the same throughout, the ratio of catalyst to peroxide increases with the amount decomposed. It appears that a high ratio is not always favourable to the reaction. Reduction of the catalyst to a lower state of oxidation is likely to be small, but perhaps the ratio of the oxidised state to the reduced state may change in favour of the latter as the concentration of peroxide is decreased. This will affect the rates of (*b'*) and (*c'*), and perhaps the overall rate of decomposition. It may be noted that the initial ratio of peroxide to catalyst in our experiments varies from 0.6 to 600 for iron, from 0.4 to 1.34 for copper, from

0.25 to 4 for manganese, and 10 to 160 for iodide. In spite of the remarks made above, we failed to detect any iodine by ordinary methods. It is doubtful therefore whether in other cases also the oxidation state is changed to any large extent. It is remarkable that in spite of such large variations in the peroxide : catalyst ratio, the apparent first order k should be so substantially constant in some cases.

The experiments with ferric and copper sulphates were repeated at other temperatures also, and the apparent energy of activation calculated from the changing k , with the following results.

TABLE III

Conc. of ferric sulphate	...	0.025 N	0.05 N	0.075 N
Energy, E (cal./mole)	...	13300	13100	12900
Conc. of copper sulphate	...	0.15 N	0.25 N	0.50 N
Energy, E (cal./mole)	...	19000	18900	18900

The apparent energy of activation in presence of copper ions is appreciably higher than that in presence of ferric ions. If the mechanism of reaction with copper ions is substantially similar to ferric ions, discussed in the beginning, the actions in mixed solutions are likely to be additive. This was satisfactorily borne out from some of our experiments in which the mixture was made 0.1 N-H₂O₂, 0.025 N-ferric sulphate and 0.5 N-copper sulphate. When the rates for the two salts are separately calculated for hydrogen peroxide left at the moment (obtained from two separate experiments, one for iron and the other for copper ions), the overall rate agrees with the sum of the calculated rates. The additivity, however, breaks down at low concentrations of H₂O₂ (Fig. 4).

FIG. 4

Catalysis by Fe₂(SO₄)₃ + CuSO₄.

It seems that the simple mechanism, outlined above, is sufficient to explain the general observations. Fe³⁺ may be changed by any other ion which can readily change

its state of oxidation. We tried a number of salts in moderate concentrations which do not possess this property, viz., $MgSO_4$, $MgCl_2$, $CaCl_2$, $ZnSO_4$, $NiCl_2$, $NiSO_4$, $NaCl$, KCl and Na_2SO_4 , but in none of these cases did we observe any catalytic effect. The adverse effect of H^+ ions on the decomposition is clearly seen (Eq. a) and the fundamental similarity between the actions of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} ions is understood. Introduction of OH^- ions would shift the equilibrium in (a) to the right, providing a large concentration of O_2^{2-} , and oxygen may be liberated according to (b') even if a trace of catalyst is present in preference to (b), which would be to a certain extent depressed by large concentrations of OH^- ions. According to this mechanism, relatively high concentrated solutions of hydrogen peroxide may be more stable in complete absence of a catalyst, as is well known (Mellor, *loc. cit.*).

On the other hand, Haber and Weiss (*loc. cit.*) and Barb *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) insist that the mechanism involves the production of free radicals (OH , HO_2) and subsequent setting up of reaction chains. One of the evidences pointed out by Barb *et al.* is that H_2O_2 , catalysed by an iron salt, can initiate polymerisation, e.g., of acrylonitrile, such polymerisation being characteristic of free radicals. However, by suitable choice of concentrations there is no polymerisation at all. Haber and Weiss (*loc. cit.*) refer to the phenomenon of 'Katalasestoss', observed by Kuhu and Wassermann (*Annalen*, 1933, 503, 203). Obviously, the explanation given by Haber and Weiss for the abnormal increase in rate of decomposition is far from simple. The conditions suggested by them are: (i) a high concentration of H_2O_2 ; (ii) a low concentration of Fe^{3+} such as may be existing in ferric acetate or succinate; (iii) an Fe^{2+} remover, e.g. $\gamma\gamma'$ -dipyridyl. When these external materials are introduced into the system, it is doubtful whether their action can be regarded as merely adjusting the concentrations concerned. At low concentrations (e.g. 0.05 M) $FeCl_3$ is likely to hydrolyse quickly (Gyani *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). It appears to us that an important aspect concerning the state of catalysing ions has been ignored in these discussions. It appears quite likely that ion pairs, triplets, etc. may exist in solutions when conditions are appropriate. It is also likely that interionic distances in these pairs may change with concentration, ionic strength and other conditions, and it may be only with selected values of these distances and configurations that catalysis may be favoured. It does not appear justified that Balandin's views concerning catalysis by solids (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, B2, 289) should be completely ignored for solutions. 'Katalasestoss' may well be explained on the basis of such favoured conditions existing in particular mixtures.

In any case, there is no denying that even for solutions there is a good deal of specificity observed. Indeed, some old observations on the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 are remarkable. Thus, finely divided platinum, manganese dioxide and charcoal powder are catalysts and perhaps to a lesser extent so are finely divided iron and copper, cerium and manganese in neutral solutions. Among oxides of copper, cerium, manganese and iron, the best is MnO_2 followed by CuO , CeO_2 and Fe_2O_3 . This is precisely the reverse order for the corresponding cations in solution, Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . We find from our preliminary work that the activity of an oxide decreases as the water content is decreased by heating at increasing temperatures, which is likely

to affect lattice dimensions of the solids. It appears that a larger stress on physical conditions of catalysts, both in the solid state and in solutions, is necessary and little purpose is served in analysing data from a limited number of experiments. Even Haber and Weiss appear to realise this situation (*loc. cit.*, p. 348).

The falling off of the first order velocity constant at lower concentrations of H_2O_2 recalls the similar observation with homogeneous gas reactions. The well-known explanation in the latter case due to Lindemann (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1922, 17, 598) is that in the first place activated molecules of the reactants are formed, but not all of them decompose to yield the desired products. If most of them revert to the unactivated condition before reaction takes place, the process, which may be bimolecular as to the activation process, may appear as unimolecular as to decomposition. Since deactivation would be less frequent at low pressures, if a stationary state is attained, the rate of reaction would approach the rate of activation so that the order would tend to be 2, and a fall in the first order rate constant would be observed if an attempt is made to set down the data in accordance with such a process. The presence of water molecules in the reaction mixture offsets a simple explanation of the falling k on these lines, but the situation still points out that the H_2O_2 molecules may be in an activated condition in reaction (c').

It appears therefore that the energies of activation, we have determined above, correspond to the activation of H_2O_2 molecules, and the chief function of a catalyst may be to lower this value. In such a case, one may look out for an association of the catalysing ion with the peroxide molecule, resulting in the formation of a charged complex. We should then expect salt effects. This matter is receiving our attention. We may add that we have secured definite evidence of such effects in the heterogeneous catalysis in presence of CuO .

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